

Merit-Based Admission Policy in District Boarding Schools: A case study of Magawa Secondary School in Central West Education, Malawi

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ARTICLE INFORMATION	ABSTRACT
<p>Article history: Published on 05 Sep 2025</p> <p>Keywords: Admission Selection Application Letters Suspension Exclusion Quality education</p>	<p>This study examines the impact of merit-based admissions on student outcomes, behavior, and resource utilization in district boarding schools, with Magawa Secondary School serving as a case study. The study used mixed research approach and employed a case study method. Data were obtained from the surveys, in-depth interviews, focus group discussions and documentary analysis from head teacher, 3 heads of departments, 12 teachers and 21 learners from F2, F3 and F4 classes. The integration of descriptive and inferential statistics was pivotal in shaping the conclusions of the research findings. Descriptive statistics provided a clear snapshot of the academic performance metrics, such as Malawi School Certificate Education pass rates, public university selection rates, and disciplinary cases. This type of analysis effectively highlighted the disparities in key variables between the two groups of students. The use of inferential statistics, specifically the overall percentages, allowed for the determination of whether the observed differences in were significant. The results indicate that selected students outperform their peers, achieving a pass rate of 80.25% compared to 53.11% for admitted students at MSCE. Selected students also demonstrate higher public university selection rates (84.8% vs. 15.1%) and lower disciplinary suspension (32.77% vs. 67.22%) and exclusion rates (23.88% vs. 76.12%). Furthermore, selected students exhibit more positive behavioral patterns, including improved attendance, discipline, and engagement resulting in better academic performance than their counterparts. However, the increased enrollment resulting from admission by application letters strain school resources, highlighting the need for balanced admissions policies that consider both access and resource capacity. The findings suggest that restricting admission by application letters in Community Day Secondary Schools is a necessary evil that can maintain educational quality and promote positive student behavior in district boarding schools. Even though the study uses data from 2004 to 2014, the findings remain relevant and applicable to the present situation, considering that the Ministry of Education announced abolition of the admission policy by application starting from the 2014/2015 academic year. This study contributes to the discourse on education policy, justifying the abolition of the application-based admission policy in shaping admission policies that promote academic excellence, positive behavior, and resource sustainability in schools.</p>

1. Introduction

Since Malawi got independence in 1964, access to secondary school has always been a challenge due to admission policy issues and inadequate secondary school places. Therefore, only those best qualifying must be the ones to be promoted in the few secondary schools; making merit-based selection the only process of promoting students to secondary schools. In 1971, Government of Malawi conceived the admission policy to allow church and non-church school aged children access secondary education without necessarily joining the church. Ministry of Education used standard 8 examination results to allocate learners into different secondary schools. The best performers were admitted into mission secondary schools known as Grant-Aided Secondary Schools and in National Government Secondary Schools like Dedza Secondary School popularly known as 'Box 48' and Lilongwe Girls Secondary School. The second-best achievers were admitted into District Boarding Secondary Schools. Government deliberately selected learners to schools away from home region as a means of fostering national conscious. This policy direction made Day Secondary turn into boarding schools but with limited and sometimes with improvised boarding facilities. Eventually, most of the infrastructure developments in such type of secondary schools were left in the hands of boarding committees to engage the communities in self-help projects to provide boarding facilities.

It is worth noting that, at the conception of merit-based admission policy, government rigidly followed the policy until 1994 when Ministry of Education started admission of learners into secondary schools based on

applications letters. The rightful interpretation of the policy reads as follows:

Admission therefore refers to the process whereby Ministry of Education Science and Technology has designated authority to Education Division Managers (EDM) at Education Division Offices to admit students; who did not qualify for secondary school education through their grades at Primary School Leaving Certificate Examinations to secondary schools.

Admission was meant to take place in Community Day Secondary Schools (CDSS) and not in Convectional Secondary Schools. It is argued that the Ministry of Education was using its discretion to identify who to admit and who to reject without necessarily considering the conduct or the ability of the applicants. This resulted in more and more unqualifying primary school leavers to enter secondary schools through application letters as well.

2. Literature review

2.1 The changing face of admission from Missionary schools to modern practices

The early Christian missionaries brought about Western Education. Their admission policy a mix of religious and educational goals. Therefore, their curriculum was a combination of secular subjects and religious instruction. This made the admission policy to these schools not only inclined to academic capability, social status but also willingness to adopt Christianity as factors determining the admission policy. As a result, those families that

resisted Christianity were at pains to get their children enrolled in these missionary schools.

In contrast to the old traditional method of admitting students in missionary school, contemporary governments and educators have adopted more inclusive and merit-based admission systems. [Kezar \(2011\)](#) notes that contemporary education systems are focusing on fairness, equity, and access, by admitting students in both missionary and public schools based on students' academic achievement, standardized test scores, and other relevant criteria including entrance examinations in missionary schools. Therefore, in the present days there can be no family left out due to religious affiliations as it were before government introduced a new shift in admission procedures in 1971. [Troman \(2008\)](#) argues the importance of separating religion from education so that schools are inclusive for students for both church and nonchurch members. Notwithstanding these differences, both early Christian missionaries and modern educators consider education as the more appropriate tool for shaping individuals and societies into a transformed human being. Education empowers individuals and communities to achieve their full potential thereby providing people with survival skills in the changing world ([Bassey, 2005](#)). Many schools today value and promote qualities such as empathy, respect and responsibility for others which were at the heart of the missionary philosophical stance ([Arthur, 2014](#)).

The contrast has been that Early Christian missionaries used education to extend Christianity and its influence to the population, and this led the contemporary educators to consider and implement a student-centered focus, diversity, and inclusive form of curriculum. [Darling Hammond \(2010\)](#) underscores the inevitability of personalizing education based on a student's unique background, experience, and learning style for the better students' outcomes.

2.2 Admission policy in public secondary schools in Malawi.

Today's globalized society, realizes that knowledge and skills are key to a country's productive future ([World Bank, 2005](#)). Unfortunately, a lot of school age going youths especially in most developing countries like Malawi lack opportunities to pursue secondary school education ([World Bank, 2005](#)).

Access to formal education has always been a problem for every school aged child since the time of missionary education because missionaries wanted education for evangelism. Additionally, there were inadequate secondary school places to absorb most of the learners. This is in unison with the Phillips Commission that was set up in 1961 by the colonial masters. The commission reported that access to secondary school was very restrictive because of slow expansion of secondary schools. Therefore in 1961 Ministry of Education announced a policy that meant priority to be given to expansion of facilities for secondary education. Government of Malawi then responded by building new day secondary schools in each and every district in Malawi so that by 1966 there were 36 secondary schools across Malawi. However, these 36 secondary schools were not adequate enough to absorb most of the primary school leavers who successfully completed their studies. This made selection policy a bottom neck. Therefore, only those best qualifying were the ones to be selected in the few secondary schools. This then meant that admission to secondary school was bound to be keen. Selection therefore, became a matter of the utmost urgency and merit was the sole standard used in the process of promoting students to secondary schools. In 1971, Government of Malawi conceived the admission policy in order to allow church and non-church school aged children access secondary education without necessarily belonging to the church. Ministry of Education used standard 8 examination results to allocate learners into different secondary schools.

2.3 The concept of admission policy by application letters

Since conception of admission policy basing on merit, government rigidly followed the policy until 1994 when Ministry of Education started admission of learners into secondary schools based on applications in response to the high enrollment as a result of Free Primary School Education. In 1998, the Ministry of Education through the secondary unification policy turned all Malawi College of Distance Education Centers (DECs) to Community Day Secondary Schools (CDSS), for the successful primary school learners who did not gain the limited available secondary school places.

However, the policy implementers made the admission policy unduly complex because students were not only admitted into Community Day Secondary Schools but also in District Boarding Schools and even in

National Secondary Schools. The process of implementing the admission policy was not clear as a result it was relatively difficult for the ordinary citizens to understand the policy and its practice. It is argued that the Ministry of Education Science and Technology was using its discretion to identify who to admit and who to reject without necessarily considering the conduct or the ability of the applicants. While many qualifying primary school leavers entered secondary schools through merit, more and more unqualifying primary school leavers and also other applicants for form 2, 3 and 4 places entered secondary schools through application letters as well. While the initial concept of admission policy was meant to process screen learners, the admission policy by application letters failed ensure total quality management with the aim of upholding quality secondary school education. Regrettably, the policy has been blamed for the poor secondary school education since 1994 when it was initially introduced.

3. Methodology

3.1 Research Approach

This study adopted a mixed-methods research approach, integrating both quantitative and qualitative methods. According to Creswell and Plano [Clark \(2017\)](#), mixed-methods research delivers a complete understanding of complex phenomena by focusing on the strengths of both quantitative and qualitative approaches.

The quantitative approach involved the collection and analysis of numerical data, such as student enrollment numbers, academic performance, resource quantities and demographic information. As noted by [Bryman \(2016\)](#), quantitative research is the appropriate approach for finding patterns and relationships in large datasets. The qualitative approach, involved the collection and analysis of non-numerical data. As argued by [Denzin and Lincoln \(2017\)](#), qualitative research is best for discovering complex social phenomena and gaining insight into the suggestions and explanations of participants.

3.2 Research Design

The study adopted descriptive research design allowed the researcher to collect data to be used to describe the current state of admission policies and school classification. According to [Yin \(2018\)](#), descriptive research designs are suitable for studies that aim to describe a phenomenon or situation. As noted by [Kumar \(2019\)](#), descriptive research appropriately provides a snapshot of a phenomenon at a particular point in time. It has been well argued by [Stake \(2013\)](#), that case studies provide in-depth insights into specific contexts and can be used to develop theoretical propositions for a better understanding of the phenomena.

3.3 Target population, sample size and sampling technique

The target population for this study comprises 350 individuals, including 320 learners, 1 headteacher, 3 academic heads, and 26 teachers. From this population, a sample size of 36 individuals was selected, consisting of 1 headteacher, 3 heads of department, 8 teachers, and 18 students. This sample size represents approximately 10 % of the total target population ($35/350 \times 100$). The researcher selected learners from forms 2, 3 and 4 because they have stayed longer at a secondary school to be able to provide data on school's academic performance and discipline status. The ages of the learners were from 15 to 19 years. Ages of the teachers were not significant but rather the professional experience of the teacher in the teaching profession was significant in establishing experience of teachers and learners' achievement.

3.4 Sampling techniques

The study used purposive sampling technique. [Maxwell \(1997\)](#) defines purposive sampling as a type of sampling in which particular settings, persons or events are deliberately selected for the important information they can provide that cannot be gotten as well from other choices. The head teacher was chosen because he has all the school records from which data on academic performance and discipline in the school. The three heads of departments were chosen representing language department, humanities department and sciences department. The teachers were chosen as follows; 3 from languages, 3 from sciences and 2 from humanities because humanities offer more of the optional subjects whilst the other departments offer compulsory subjects. The learners were purposefully selected to include both selected and admitted learners. They were selected as follows; 4 boys and 4 girls from each form making a total of 8 respondents from each form and a total of 24 respondents in forms altogether. [Kombo and Tromp \(2006\)](#) assert that purposive sampling is a

non-probability form of sampling and the sample used in this study was deliberately targeted to provide valid data for the study.

3.5 Data collection

Primary data collection for this study involved a multi-method approach, incorporating surveys, interviews, and focus group discussions.

3.5.1 Focus group discussion

This provided a platform for participants to share their experiences and perceptions in a more interactive and dynamic setting. Krueger and Casey (2015) have argued that focus groups are mostly useful for collecting contextualized data and gaining insight into the perspectives and attitudes of participants. Both open-ended questions and probes were used to encourage participants to share their thoughts and opinions freely. This approach allows the researcher to gather rich, qualitative data that can provide insights into the complex issues surrounding admission policies and school classification.

3.5.2. Surveys

The survey consisted of both closed-ended and open-ended questions. A total of 12 teachers and 21 students participated in the survey, which was self-administered to ensure convenience and accessibility (Dillman et al., 2014). The survey data were analyzed using simple descriptive statistics such as comparative percentages and thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2006).

3.5.3 In-depth interviews

They were conducted with key stakeholders, such as the headteacher and heads of department, to gather detailed insights into their perspectives on admission policies and school classification.

The interviews were semi-structured, with open-ended questions designed to encourage participants to share their thoughts and opinions freely. Kvale and Brinkmann (2015), note that semi-structured interviews deliver a supple framework for data collection, allowing data collectors to probe and explore topics in depth.

3.5.4 Documentary analysis

Policy documents, such as Malawi National Examinations Board pass lists and grades, the Malawi Education Sector Plan and the National Education Policy, and the re-admission policy were also reviewed to understand the policy framework governing admission policies and school classification. The aim of studying the policies was to understand the intentions and goals of the policymakers (Patton, 2015).

3.5.5 Data analysis and interpretation

This was achieved through a systematic and rigorous process. Thematic qualitative data analysis was employed to identify, code, and categorize themes and patterns (Braun & Clarke, 2006). The data analysis process involved several stages, including data cleaning, coding, and categorization (Miles & Huberman, 1994). The coding process was iterative, with codes and themes being refined and revised as the analysis progressed (Saldaña, 2013).

The accuracy and reliability of the findings were achieved by asking participants to verify the accuracy of the findings as advocated by Guba and Lincoln (1989). This process helped to establish the credibility of the research findings.

3.6 Ethical Considerations

This study adhered to rigorous ethical standards to ensure the protection and well-being of participants. Firstly, informed consent was obtained from all participants, who were fully informed about the purpose, procedures, and potential risks and benefits of the study (National Commission for the Protection of Human Subjects of Biomedical and Behavioral Research, 1979). Secondly, participants were assured of confidentiality and anonymity, and their right to withdraw from the study at any time was respected (Wiles et al., 2006).

In addition, the researcher obtained necessary approvals from relevant authorities, including institutional research committee and ethics committees, to ensure that ethical standards are adhered to (Creswell, 2014).

4. Findings and Discussions

4.1 Findings from Primary Data

4.1.1 Themes identified in the study

The research on the admission-based application system at Magawa Boarding School has identified several key themes that provide insights into the experiences of students and teachers. These themes include:

a. Theme 1: Diverse Student Body

The admission-based application system has led to a more diverse student body at Magawa Boarding School. As a result, there has been more inclusive and dynamic learning environment because of the students that come from different backgrounds and with varying abilities.

"It is a pleasure to secure a place at a secondary school. And I feel like I have learnt more from my classmates who come from different backgrounds as a result of the admission-based application policy. It has broadened my perspective and helped me become more empathetic."

The implication is that the school should continue to promote diversity and inclusion initiatives so that even when the admission policy by application is abolished. There must be a sense of belonging among all students.

b. Theme 2: Academic Challenges and Support

On a larger scale, students who were admitted through the admission-based application system have met academic challenges, mostly in subjects that require robust foundational knowledge. However, the school has provided support systems to help students succeed.

"When I first attend the mathematics class, I struggled with subject at first, but my teacher provided extra help, and I was able to catch up."

The implication is that, the school management and subject teachers should continue to provide support systems for students who are struggling academically, such as tutoring or extra help sessions and of course without charging extra fees.

c. Theme 3: Student Engagement and Motivation

The admission-based application system has led to varying levels of student engagement and motivation. Some students are highly motivated and engaged, especially those students that were not selected in the first selection but had equally better grades, or were selected in Community Day Secondary Schools while others struggled to catch up with secondary school academic work.

"To be honest, I must say that securing secondary school place is the greatest opportunity for me to explore my interests and passions."

The implication is that, the school should devise school activities that promote student engagement and motivation by among other initiatives provide opportunities for students to explore their interests and passions.

d. Theme 4: Resource Constraints

Most admissions after first selection significantly increase school enrollment which in turn causes significant resource constraints, including shortages of essential resources such as beds, mattresses, desks, and textbooks. This is compounded with the erratic supply of these resources by the Supplies Unit at the Ministry of Education, making it a norm, leaving students and teachers to adapt to uncertain circumstances without clear solution to the challenges even in the advent of TALULAR. Even with the introduction of Parent Teachers Association funds, Magawa secondary school still has big challenge in sourcing adequate teaching and learning resources and even talk less of infrastructure development.

"We have been trained to be creative with the resources we have, but it's hard when we do not get any allocations in a particular academic year."

The implication is that the school should explore alternative funding sources and implement efficient resource management systems to address resource constraints knowing that tuition fees and boarding fees are inadequate to cover all school expenses in addition to the fact that they are designated funds for school management.

e. Theme 5: Support Systems

There is more evidence suggesting that the school has implemented various support systems to help students succeed academically and personally. These support systems include tutoring, counseling, and extracurricular activities.

"I have been able to get easy help from my form teachers, subject teachers and classmates whenever I need the help, and I have also joined a few clubs such as Wildlife and Debate Clubs that I am interested in."

The implication is that, the school should continue to provide support systems for students and explore ways to improve their effectiveness.

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4.1.2 Challenges in boarding school

The respondents were asked to state the availability of facilities in boarding school; their responses were tabulated as follows in Table 4.1

a. The situation of beds at Magawa Secondary School (2013/14)

The hotels' capacity is 380 as per bed space. In the period of study, the school records showed 171 beds against 380 bed space. This represents 45 % availability of beds and 55 % unavailability of beds. The total school enrolment recorded was 765 learners against 171 beds. This implies that the school needed 591 beds to cater for all the 765 learners. Unfortunately, girls are selected at this school as day scholars and therefore, the count of beds for girls was not part of this concern. However, this policy is resented as most girls opt for boarding places in the few available hostels; a situation that makes hostels a congested place.

Table 4.1: Availability of beds at Magawa Secondary School

Hostel	Number of beds	Hostel capacity	Shortfall
Hostel A	40	40	0
Hostel B	0	40	40
Hostel C	0	20	20
Hostel D	32	60	28
Hostel E	23	40	17
Hostel F	25	60	35
Hostel G	25	60	35
Hostel H	26	60	34
Totals	171	380	209

Source: Research data, 2014

b. Situation of mattresses at Magawa Secondary School

Respondents revealed that there are enough mattresses for each of them but with very few beds. There are usually two learners sleeping on one bed,

Table 4.2: School enrollment and number of teaching staff at Magawa

Yr	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014
Enlr.	480	460	470	414	568	564	549	572	537	765
Tea.	19	19	20	20	22	21	21	23	23	26

(Source: MoEST, Statistical returns for secondary schools, 2005 – 2014)

According to the matrix from Ministry of Education, Magawa Secondary School should have 18 teachers to suffice the requirement. Magawa Secondary school is a double stream school and a single shift, therefore the number of teachers required is 18. Therefore, the question of under staffing does not arise at Magawa Secondary School because there have been between 19 and 26 teachers from 2005 to 2014.

4.2.3 Academic performance from 2005 to 2014

While both the average percentage and the overall pass percentage can be useful in this research, depending on the context and purpose of the study, the overall pass percentage is more relevant and meaningful. The overall pass percentage gives a clear picture of the proportion of students who passed out of the total number of students which is useful for understanding the overall performance.

a. MSCE pass rate (2005 – 2014)

Table 4.3: MSCE pass rate from selection list

Year	Selection	Pass	% pass
2005	76	62	81.58
2006	91	79	86.81
2007	89	74	83.15
2008	78	56	71.79
2009	94	76	80.85
2010	87	69	79.31
2011	88	71	80.68
2012	87	65	74.71
2013	81	63	77.78
2014	90	76	84.44
Total	861	689	80.25

Source: Research data, 2014

Making a comparison to national average the pass rate of 80.25% is significantly higher than the national average of 54.79% in 2024. This suggests that the students in this group performed exceptionally well compared to the national performance.

while other learners use mattresses without the beds. Again, this is a health hazard as the floors are not frequently mopped because there are so many mattresses in a single room.

c. Situation of dining hall at Magawa Secondary School

The research findings show that Magawa Boarding School does not have a dining hall. Unfortunately, this has been in the design of all the district boarding schools. The reason is that government recognizes national boarding schools and not district boarding schools. District boarding secondary schools are left in the hands of the local community to develop them. As a result of having no dining hall learners take their meals under the tree and in unprotected areas. Learners are forced to take their meals into the hostels during the rainy season and in cold season. It becomes a health risk to use hostels as a dining room. However, there is direct relation between admission policy and dining hall because Ministry of Education selects and admits learners as boarders at Magawa Secondary School. Therefore, a dining hall is a facility required for a boarding school.

d. Situation of latrines, bathrooms and teaching and learning resources

The findings further reveal that latrines, bathrooms and teaching and learning materials are available but not adequate and not to standards in some cases. However, the researcher would not quantify the numbers of some of the facilities like bathrooms, latrines and teaching and learning materials. It shows that numbers of the facilities as revealed from conversations with participants, do not match with the number of the learners using the facilities. In adequateness of the latrines, bathrooms and beds compromise sanitation resulting in a health hazard environment. When learners frequently become ill, they fail to attend classes.

4.2 Findings from Secondary Data

4.2.1 Number of teachers at Magawa

Table 4.4: MSCE pass rate from admission list

Year	Admission	Pass	% pass
2005	56	31	55.36
2006	50	16	32
2007	22	9	40.9
2008	17	6	35.29
2009	71	52	73.24
2010	74	44	59.46
2011	43	26	60.47
2012	54	29	53.7
2013	74	39	52.7
2014	102	47	46.08
	563	299	53.11

Source: Research data, 2014

Making a comparison with the 2024 MSCE pass rate which was 54.79%, the overall pass percentage of 53.11% is slightly lower than the national pass rate of 54.79% in 2024. This suggests that, on average, the performance of the students in this group is slightly below the national average. One possible implication is due to different student entry point as a result of admission policy by application letters.

This therefore, suggests that we further examine the individual percentages to identify patterns or areas for improvement. For example, some sets had much lower percentages (e.g., 32% and 35.29%), which could indicate specific challenges or areas for targeted support.

b. Public university selection 2005 -2014

The research wanted to establish numbers of admitted students that got selected to Public University Colleges of Malawi, namely University of Malawi, The Malawi University of Business and Science, Kamuzu College of Nursing, Lilongwe University of Agriculture and Natural resources and Mzuzu University.

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Table 4.5 Public University from selected list

Year	Total selection	University	From selection list	%
2005	2		2	100
2006	3		3	100
2007	3		3	100
2008	4		4	100
2009	3		3	100
2010	5		4	80
2011	7		6	85.7
2012	13		10	76.9
2013	12		10	83.3
2014	14		11	78.57
Total	66		56	84.8

Source: Research data, 2014

Comparison to 2024 NCHE National Selection

According to the 2024/25 selection results, the National Council for Higher Education (NCHE) selected 12,819 students out of 24,582 qualified applicants to public universities, representing national selection rate at 52.16%. Making a comparison of the two selection rates, Magawa's selection rate is approximately 84.85%, which is significantly higher than the national selection rate of 52.16% in 2024/25.

This suggests that the students in this group had a much higher success rate in being selected for public universities compared to the national average.

Table 4.6 Public university from admission list

Year	Total selection	University	From admission list	%
2005	2		0	0
2006	3		0	0
2007	3		0	0
2008	4		0	0
2009	3		0	0
2010	5		1	20
2011	7		1	14.2
2012	13		3	23.07
2013	12		2	16.66
2014	14		3	21.42
Total	66		10	15.1

(Source: Head teacher's records, Magawa, 2014)

Comparison to 2024 NCHE Public University Selection:

In 2024, out of 24,582 students who qualified for selection, 12,819 students were but specifically selected for universities, representing 52.16%. In making comparison with the two selection rates, Magawa selection rate in this group is approximately 15.15%, which is significantly lower than the national selection rate of 52.16% for public universities in 2024.

This suggests that the students in this group had a much lower success rate in being selected for public universities compared to the national average.

c. Deviant behavior from 2005 to 2014

Data was collected by examining the school's suspension file. The study wanted to find out the frequency of deviant behaviors at the school shown by admitted learner.

Table 4.7 Number of suspended from selected list

Year	Total # suspended	# suspended from selected list	%
2005	14	6	42.85
2006	8	5	62.5
2007	16	9	56.25
2008	13	5	38.46
2009	19	7	36.84
2010	32	11	34.37
2011	44	6	13.63
2012	14	3	21.4
2013	11	4	36.36
2014	9	3	33.33
Total	180	59	32.77

Source: Research data, 2025

The data suggests that even students from selected list had students that were prone to disciplinary issues at 32.77%.

Table 4.8: # suspended from admission list

Year	Total # suspended	# suspended from admission list	%
2005	14	8	57.14
2006	8	3	37.5
2007	16	7	43.75
2008	13	8	61.53
2009	19	12	63.15
2010	44	38	86.36
2011	32	21	65.62
2012	14	11	78.57
2013	11	7	63.63
2014	9	6	66.66
Total	180	121	67.22

Source: Research data, 2014

The data suggests that more students from admission list were prone to disciplinary issues at 67.22%.

Table 4.9 Total # excluded from selection list

Year	Excluded	# excluded from selection list	%
2005	8	2	25
2006	12	3	41.67
2007	9	2	66.67
2008	4	1	25
2009	5	2	75
2010	11	3	63.64
2011	9	2	22.22
2012	4	0	0
2013	2	0	0
2014	3	1	33.33
Total	67	16	23.88

Source: Research data, 2014

The data suggests that even the selected list of students some were prone to disciplinary issues that warranted exclusion at 23.88%

Table 4.10: Comparative number of deviant behaviour (excluded) Number excluded from the admission list

Year	Total excluded	# excluded from admission list	%
2005	8	6	75
2006	12	9	75
2007	9	7	77.78
2008	4	3	75
2009	5	2	40
2010	11	8	72.73
2011	9	7	77.78
2012	4	4	100
2013	2	4	100
2014	3	2	66.67
Total	67	51	76.12

Source: Research data, 2014

The data suggests that there were more students from the admission list that were more prone to disciplinary issues that warranted exclusion at 76.12%. One possible explanation is that some of the excluded students were those transferred from other schools upon expiry of their suspension period; a policy implemented at the Ministry of Education.

Types of offences warranting suspension and exclusion

Table 4.11 shows the frequency of offences that warranted suspension and exclusion from school in the period 2005 to 2014.

Table 4.11: Types of offences

Type of offence	Frequency	% represented
Teasing and bullying	32	17.7
Alcohol and substance abuse	21	11.6
Pregnancy	16	8.8
Spending night without exist slip	6	3.3
Vandalism and strikes	102	56.6
Serious theft	3	1.6
Total	180	100

Source: Research data, 2014

5. Summary, Conclusion and recommendations

5.1 Summary

This study investigated the impact of merit-based admissions on student outcomes, behavior, and resource utilization in district boarding schools, with Magawa Secondary School serving as a case study. The findings revealed that selected students outperformed their peers in terms of academic achievement, university selection rates, and behavioral patterns. However, the increased enrollment resulting from merit-based admissions strained school resources, highlighting the need for balanced admissions policies.

5.2 Conclusion

The study concludes that merit-based admissions can be an effective strategy for improving student outcomes and promoting positive behavior in district boarding schools. However, it also highlights the need for careful consideration of resource capacity to ensure sustainable growth and quality education. The findings suggest that admission by application letters should be restricted to Community Day Secondary Schools where the policy was meant to be enforced as CDSS were meant to serve the local communities.

5.3 Recommendations

1. Ministry to develop and implement a balanced admissions policy that considers both merit and resource capacity to ensure sustainable growth and quality education.
2. Ministry of Education should allocate resources effectively to support the increased enrollment, including infrastructure, teacher training, and educational materials.
3. The Ministry should provide student support services, such as counseling and academic support, to promote positive behavior and academic achievement.
4. The Ministry of Education should establish a monitoring and evaluation system to track the impact of admission by application letters on student outcomes, behaviour and resource utilization.
5. The Ministry of Education should provide capacity-building programs for teachers and staff to enhance their skills in managing diverse student needs.

5.4 Implications for Policy and Practice

1. Ministry of Education need to use evidence-based decision-making to inform admissions policies and ensure that they are aligned with the school's resource capacity.
2. The Ministry need to make prioritize resource sustainability to ensure that the school can provide quality education to all students.

5.5 Future Research Directions

1. Future research should explore the effectiveness of different admissions

policies in various school settings.

2. Future research should investigate how effective the Ministry of Education is implementing the directive on abolition of admission policy by application letters in secondary schools across the country.

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